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A Narrative Review on Teleoncology Enhancing Cancer Care and Equity in Indigenous Communities and Geographically Isolated Areas

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ABSTRACT

Background: This paper reviews the perks and challenges of cancer care for patients in geographically isolated areas of India during the COVID-19 pandemic and India's efforts to ensure health access through telehealth services. **Methodology:** This narrative review applied Andersen Newman's Health Service Utilization Model and the Healthcare Access Barrier framework. Eleven empirical studies were purposively selected through systematic searches in PubMed, Science Direct, Oxford Academic, and Google Scholar. It examines how to ensure equitable access through teleoncology in geographically isolated areas. Moreover, it discussed the significance of teleoncology in ensuring equity in health distribution during this period. **Results & Discussion:** It highlighted reduced health access due to barriers such as socioeconomic challenges, limited awareness, cultural beliefs, and geographical obstacles. Teleoncology, through platforms like eSanjeevani, emerged as a solution, offering remote consultations, chemotherapy supervision, and multidisciplinary care. The study discussed benefits like reduced travel costs, improved early diagnosis, and continuous care, but also noted challenges like digital literacy, technical issues, and infrastructure gaps. **Recommendations:** Recommendations include utilizing existing infrastructure, enhancing internet connectivity, and developing a skilled workforce to establish a robust teleoncology model in India, ensuring equitable access to cancer care for underserved populations.

Keywords: Teleoncology, COVID-19 pandemic, cancer care, geographically isolated areas, healthcare access.

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Introduction

Despite the presence of health insurance schemes such as PMJAY and state-funded healthcare, cancer treatment remains a significant challenge for many Indians. Research indicates that limited cancer screening awareness, social stigma, and mistrust in healthcare providers hinder access to care¹. Additionally, cultural beliefs and geographical barriers further exacerbate these issues. In India, the alarming increased incidence of cancer reported by Vinay et al. (2015)² is from 12.7 million to 21 million by 2030. These projections are corroborated by data from the National Cancer Registry Program (NCRP) (Indian Council of Medical Research [ICMR], 2020³. Mathur et al. (2020)⁴ reported a cancer incidence rate of 98.7 per 100,000 people in 2020, with an estimated 679,421 males and 712,758 females diagnosed. The situation is projected to worsen, with an estimated doubling of the cancer burden from 2.4 million in 2020 to 4.8 million by 2050⁵. Hence, the healthcare services were broken during the pandemic due to the government's policies on preventing the pandemic. However, the telehealth services became an alternative health delivery system and displaced traditional health services, ensuring accessibility and availability of healthcare services in India. This is an acceptable health access to reach the hard-to-reach populations during the pandemic.

Understanding the advantages of telehealth services, this narrative review is an effort to discuss the implementation of teleoncology in the indigenous and geographically isolated areas in India to ensure accessibility and affordability of oncology services. Thus, this review (1) examine the disruptions in cancer care during the COVID-19 pandemic; (2) explore the emergence and integration of teleoncology services; (3) evaluate the benefits and limitations of telemedicine in oncology care; and (4) assess India's digital health strategies in promoting equitable access to cancer services for underserved populations, such as Indigenous communities. In addition, the article discussed the role of teleoncology to ensure equitable healthcare delivery, access to cancer care for vulnerable populations, notably indigenous communities and individuals in geographically isolated regions, whose health services are disproportionately affected by geographical and logistical impediments to accessing specialized tertiary medical services.

Methodology

This review examines how telehealth services contributed to healthcare access for India's indigenous population during the COVID-19 pandemic. It utilizes Andersen Newman's health service utilization model and the healthcare access barrier model to highlight the importance of factors like income, availability of professionals and facilities, and waiting times. A key focus is the urgent need for a national teleoncology platform, particularly for geographically isolated indigenous communities in regions such as Lakshadweep and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands.

Articles for this review were gathered from Science Direct, Oxford University Press (via MyLOFT), Google Scholar, and PubMed, with a publication date restriction of 2020-2024 for specific searches. A systematic retrieval process used general keywords and Boolean operators to identify relevant sources on cancer care, telehealth, and healthcare access during the pandemic. Specific search terms included "screening cancer in India," "teleoncology services," and "teleoncology" on PubMed. An advanced Boolean search on the same platform targeted pandemic-related health barriers using terms like "Covid-19," "Fear," "Stigma," "Hospital," "Healthcare," and "Access." Science Direct searches focused on "Telehealth service utilization of Indigenous population during the COVID-19 pandemic in India." Oxford Academic Press searches included "Health Determinants (AND) Barriers (AND) Scheduled tribe women (AND) India (AND) Open Access (AND) Free", covering literature from 2000-2019. Grey literature, such as the National Report on Cancer and e-Sanjeevani portal documentation, was also consulted via Google and Google Scholar

Table-1: Selected empirical studies

Title, Year Published	Author (s)	Article Type/ Studies Conducted at/Population / Studies included	Findings
Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on cancer surgery: Patient's perspective, 2021	Shiv Raja, Naseem Akhtar, Abhilasha Tripathi.... Mohit Singh	Cross-sectional study, India/ 310 cases	The COVID-19 pandemic negatively impacted cancer patients by worsening financial conditions, limiting access to healthcare, and increasing psychological distress, including stress, anxiety, and depression. Those most affected included low-income individuals, married patients, and those living in rural areas. All age groups experienced difficulty in health access, with significant effects on the availability of surgical cancer care.
Impact of COVID-19 on Outcomes for Patients With Cervical Cancer in India, 2021	Nidhi Gupta, Akashdeep Singh Chauhan, Shankar,Prinja, Awadhesh Kumar Pandey	Cohort study, India	The study emphasized that delays in cervical cancer diagnosis and treatment during the pandemic could cause a 2.52 to 3.80 per cent rise in mortality, with considerable losses in life-years and disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs). These indirect effects on cancer care were found to exceed the number of COVID-19 deaths potentially prevented by pandemic restrictions, highlighting the critical need for health system reforms to ensure uninterrupted cancer care during future public health emergencies.

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Bridging the distance: a prospective tele-oncology study in Northern Norway, 2012	Tom Donnem, Bente Ervik, Kathrine Magnussen, Tone Nordoy	Prospective registration study, Norway, 101 Patient, 7 health care provider	Videoconferencing improved healthcare delivery by boosting provider confidence, enhancing patient care in most cases, and significantly reducing both waiting times and the need for transfers to tertiary hospitals.
Drivers and barriers of patients' acceptance of video consultation in cancer care, 2022	Angelina Nurtsch, Martin Teufel, Lisa MariaJahre. Alexander Bäuerle	A cross-sectional online-based survey, Germany, 350 cancer patients	In this paper, a majority of cancer patients (56 per cent) showed high acceptance of video consultations. Acceptance was influenced by factors such as age, gender, disease stage, digital confidence, and eHealth literacy. The study supports video consultations as a feasible supplement to in-person oncology care.
Teleoncology: A Solution for Everyone? A Single-Center Experience with Telemedicine during the Corona virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Pandemic, 2022	Paula Ribera, Sandra Soriano, Carla Climent, ..., Carles Pericay	Descriptive cross sectional studies, Spain, 487 cancer patients	Patients reported high satisfaction with telemedicine, and 60 per cent were willing to use it post-pandemic. However, older individuals and breast cancer patients were less likely to adopt it, indicating the need for personalised strategies. While patients preferred face-to-face consultations for complex information, they accepted telemedicine for sharing test results.
Telehealth in radiation oncology at the Townsville Cancer Centre: Service evaluation and patient satisfaction, 2019	Elizabeth Hamilton, Ellie Van Veldhuizen, Amy Brown, Sean Brennan, Sabe Sabesan	Retrospective study, Australia/ 311 patient charts	Telehealth services were delivered to 833 cancer patients, mainly males with a median age of 65, covering various cancer types and including curative radiation therapy for 60 per cent. High satisfaction was reported, with most patients preferring telehealth or a hybrid model of care.
Cost savings from a telemedicine model of care in northern Queensland, Australia, 2013	Darshit A Thaker, Richard Monypenny, Ian Olver and Sabe Sabesan	Retrospective cost-savings analysis. Australia/ 147 patient records	The teleoncology model at Townsville Cancer Centre achieved significant cost savings by reducing travel expenses. Over 56 months, it avoided \$762,394 in travel costs, resulting in a net saving of \$320,118, mainly due to decreased travel for patients, escorts, and oncologists.
Telemammography for breast cancer screening: a cost-effective approach in Argentina, 2021	Victoria Alba Malek Pascha, Li Sun, Ramiro Gilardino, Rosa Legood	A cost-utility analysis, Argentina/ 1000 cancer patients	Telemammography is more cost-effective than traditional mammography for at-risk Argentinian women over 40, offering better health outcomes at a lower cost. It improves access to care in remote areas and meets WHO cost-effectiveness thresholds in nearly 60 per cent of cases.
Cervical Cancer Screening & Associated Barriers among Women in India: A Generalized Structural Equation Modeling Approach, 2022	Nilima, Kalaivani Mani, Siddharth Kaushik, Shesh Nath Rai	Cross-sectional study, India/ 699, 686 cases	The study revealed that cervical cancer screening is influenced by factors such as age, BMI, religion, education, STI awareness, contraception use, number of children, and wealth. Women who were wealthier or Muslim had higher screening rates. Additionally, contraception use and number of children acted as key mediators, suggesting they are important focus areas for improving screening efforts.
Perceptions and acceptance of telemedicine among medical oncologists before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in Turkey, 2021	Elif Sahin, Umut Kefeli, Devrim Cabuk, Ercan Ozden, Yagmur Cakmak, Mohd. Ali Kaypak, Mustafa Seyyar, Kazım Uygun	Cross-sectional survey, TURKEY/ 110 health care provider	Telemedicine use increased significantly during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for clinical visits and multidisciplinary meetings. Oncologists developed a more positive outlook on telemedicine, with expectations of its continued use after the pandemic.

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Remote Monitoring and Holistic Care of Home-Isolated COVID-19 Positive Healthcare Workers Through Digital Technology During the Omicron (B.1.1.529) Wave: A Prospective Cohort Study From India, 2022	Siddharth Jain, Amit Agarwal, Anupriya Bhardwaj, Pvm Lakshmi, Manvi Singh, Anil Chauhan, Meenu Singh	Prospective cohort study , INDIA/ 1994	The study confirmed the feasibility of remote tele-monitoring for healthcare workers with mild COVID-19 in home isolation, with no cases progressing to moderate or severe illness. The model effectively addressed participants' psychosocial concerns. Additionally, symptomatic individuals were found to have a higher BMI than their asymptomatic counterparts.
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The inclusion criteria focused on original research articles, systematic reviews, commentaries, and editorials published in English and directly relevant to the scope of the review. These included studies addressing teleoncology, digital health interventions during the pandemic and healthcare access among Indigenous and geographically isolated populations in India. In line with the study objectives, purposive sampling was employed to select 11 empirical articles (**Table-1**) from 497 retrieved records. The literature chosen provided critical insights into the benefits and limitations of teleoncology services and the role of India's digital health infrastructure in addressing pandemic-induced disruptions in cancer care delivery.

The recommendations in this narrative review were developed using a combined approach involving a Modified Delphi Method and an Expert Panel Review. The first author independently drafted initial recommendations based on the review findings, and the article was sent to the third author through email, where the third author rated and commented on each statement's clarity, relevance, and feasibility. These comments revised the recommendations, and the article's final version was discussed with the second author. These face to face discussions with the second author ensured thematic coherence and contextual relevance. Only those recommendations that received complete agreement from all three authors were included in the final set. Time line of this consensus for recommendation is illustrated in **Table- 2**.

Table -2: Time line of the Consensus meeting and decision making

Phase	Activity	Authors	Duration
Phase 1: Drafting	Initial drafting of recommendations based on thematic findings of the review	1 st author	7 days
Phase 2: First Review Round	Recommendations shared via email; clarity, relevance, and feasibility rated and commented on	3 rd author	14 days
Phase 3: Revision	Recommendations revised based on third author's feedback	1 st author	5 days
Phase 4: Face-to- Face Review	In-person discussion of revised recommendations for thematic coherence and contextual relevance	1 st and 2 nd authors	3 days
Phase 5: Final Agreement	Final review and unanimous approval of recommendations	All three authors	2 days

Results

This study's findings were derived from the comprehensive analysis of 11 empirical studies to ascertain the significance of teleoncology care services for India's indigenous and geographically isolated communities. Additionally, the paper incorporated eight review papers, two commentaries, one perspective, one editorial, and a single website to support the findings of the empirical studies and generate a comprehensive discussion on the teleoncology services for the indigenous and geographically isolated communities.

Broken Chain of Cancer Care during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A significant reduction in health access from March 1, 2020, to May 31, 2020⁸ led to suspending cancer care services or referrals to other health facilities. This reduction in health access during this period impacted both rural and urban areas, but rural populations were less privileged^{8,9}. Contributing factors such as fear of COVID-19 infection⁸, travel restrictions, lockdown measures to control the pandemic, social distancing, and economic challenges created additional barriers to accessing healthcare services. Furthermore, restrictions on accompanying attendants and visitor allowances in healthcare settings exacerbated the situation. An average delay of 3.22 days (± 0.26) in diagnosing COVID-19 also influences healthcare access.⁸

Expansion of telemedicine amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: During the COVID-19 pandemic, telehealth services were crucial in providing physical and psychological health. These services facilitate remote supervision of chemotherapy, symptom management, and palliative care^{10,16,9,11,12}. Additionally, the adoption of telehealth methods has facilitated multidisciplinary board meetings, patient follow-up through interview questionnaires¹², and telepathology services¹³ through telehealth services, known as teleoncology services. Although teleoncology is still an emerging component of healthcare services⁹, some researchers^{14,10,15,16} have highlighted its role in facilitating access to oncology professionals for patients in remote areas. This enables general practitioners to review diagnostic reports and treatment plans.

As Gupta et al. (2021)¹⁰ noted, general practitioners in local health facilities can access cancer care specialists via virtual or telephone consultations. This approach reduces the need for specialists to be physically present to assess health records^{14,12} and facilitates communication among healthcare professionals from different locations¹⁴. Videoconferencing for multidisciplinary tumour board (MDT) meetings has been particularly valuable in low-income areas, as Elder et al. (2023)¹³ reported. Furthermore, the study by Ribera et al. (2022)¹⁶ supports the argument that telehealth services effectively improve healthcare access.

Perks and Challenges of Teleoncology Services

Perks: Teleoncology has emerged as a viable and efficient approach for mitigating financial strain and improving healthcare accessibility, particularly for those residing in remote regions. By enabling virtual consultations within local healthcare facilities, the necessity for travel and associated costs, such as shipping human tissue samples for expert opinion, effectively diminishes¹⁷, including out-of-pocket expenses^{13,18}. This model is a promising strategy to address the disparities between rural and urban healthcare systems, significantly reducing the need for extensive travel and additional expenditures such as overnight stays^{19,20}.

Upgrading rural and hard-to-reach health facilities to support teleoncology has resulted in significant improvements in healthcare delivery, including early diagnosis and continuous care²¹. Teleoncology enables remote consultations, assistance with surgical procedures, and review of diagnostic reports, reducing the necessity of in-person treatments for treatments such as chemotherapy and follow-ups¹⁸. Moreover, modernizing these facilities enhances family involvement in patient care, increases satisfaction with virtual consultations and prescriptions, and alleviates stress among family members^{14,12}.

The effectiveness of teleoncology also varies with demographic factors, such as age, gender, and educational status. Ribera et al. (2022)¹⁶ noted that younger adults are more comfortable with telehealth, whereas Nurtsch et al. (2024)¹⁵ reported high acceptance among females and those with higher eHealth literacy and digital confidence. The stage of disease also plays a crucial role in accepting virtual consultations, as Tsagkaris et al. (2023)¹² demonstrated. During the COVID-19 pandemic, patients requiring palliative care expressed satisfaction with telehealth services, highlighting the viability of mHealth applications and wearable technologies for health monitoring¹⁸.

The replacement of traditional face-to-face consultations with virtual queues has further reduced patient burden, as Sabesan and Kelly (2014)²² acknowledged and emphasised the need for upgraded infrastructure in rural and remote areas to support specialist consultations and teleradiology^{19,21}. Advanced technologies, including telesurgery, virtual microscopies, and robotic telesurgery, have further expanded the potential of telehealth. For example, Malek Pascha et al. (2021)²³ reported that, compared with traditional mammography screening, telemammography yielded a more significant number of quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) per £19.92 invested among at-risk Argentinian women aged over 40.

Challenges

Dumkey et al. (2023) and Nilima et al. (2022)^{24, 1} explained that socio-demographic factors, including age, education, culture, and financial status, significantly impact access to cancer screening services. In addition, Nilima et al. (2022)²⁴ highlighted economic challenges, lack of awareness, and neglect of malignancy symptoms as having a significant role in determining participation in screening programs.

Shirke, Shaikh and Harky (2020)¹¹ focused on the linguistic differences between patients and health professionals, highlighting the need to prevent miscommunication and anxiety, particularly among ethnic minority groups. The challenges of accessing telehealth include the absence of physical examinations^{11,12} and resentment in patient interactions²⁵.

The obligation to access health services involves expanding the knowledge and accessibility of telehealth services to achieve universal health coverage⁶. However, teleoncology services often overlook patients with disabilities, such as hearing, vision, or cognitive impairments^{16,11}. Structural deficiencies, such as inadequate diagnostic facilities, screening programs and long distances to tertiary health facilities, further hinder effective cancer screening²⁶.

A significant barrier to telehealth utilization is the lack of technical knowledge among beneficiaries, which can impede its effectiveness¹⁶. Technical issues, such as problems with camera functionality, reflect broader barriers in health service utilization, as outlined by Andersen Newman's framework⁶ and the HCAB model¹⁴. Infrastructure deficiencies, such as unstable internet connections or a lack of appropriate devices, also pose significant challenges, affecting the quality of shared images and patient care^{13,11}.

India's Digital Health Response during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted global and domestic challenges in digital healthcare adoption²⁷ while simultaneously accelerating eHealth use, with internet-based healthcare services and frontline worker interventions becoming crucial²⁷. Remote monitoring has emerged as a cost-effective strategy for reducing hospitalisations²⁸. Networked hospital infrastructure facilitated by internet connectivity, exemplified by India's eSanjeevani and state-owned eHealthcare systems, proved essential. However, the eSanjeevani portal offers limited cancer care services beyond Tamil Nadu's Radiation Oncology eSanjeevani OPD²⁹.

Telehealth is increasingly important due to the projected global shortage of healthcare professionals, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Digital health platforms can enhance professional development and public health education. While India's level of telehealth adoption remains low, widespread implementation in LMICs could expand access to specialists (e.g., virtual tumour boards) and reduce unnecessary hospitalisations for advanced cancer patients³⁰.

Government initiatives, such as rural broadband expansion, mobile infrastructure development, and the Digital Village scheme, target the digital divide²⁹. Addressing digital literacy is crucial for overcoming infrastructural barriers and facilitating community access⁷. This maximises the benefits of telehealth. India's COVID-19 response included the Arogyasetu self-assessment app and the eSanjeevani consultation platform²⁷. Although eSanjeevani has facilitated more than 22 million virtual consultations, oncology-specific services are limited. The platform (eSanjeevani AB-HWC) offers several features for primary cancer screening and psychological support²⁹.

Discussion

Teleoncology services can increase health equity (SDG 3) by providing equitable access to cancer care regardless of socioeconomic status, geographic location, gender, or caste. Expanding teleoncology services across India, particularly in Indigenous community areas, can ensure continuous care for cancer patients. In support of this claim, studies by Sirintrapun & Lopez¹⁸ indicated that teleoncology could extend care from tertiary to primary care facilities. This extension facilitates remote monitoring of patient health status via mobile phones or laptops, enabling remote consultations, chemotherapy supervision, symptom management, and palliative care, thus ensuring continuous cancer care at the primary care level.

This review underscores the critical need for increased collaboration between public and private healthcare facilities in teleoncology. Economic disparities, insufficient knowledge about teleoncology services, and communication hurdles exacerbate

access to cancer care^{24,11}. Notably, this analysis highlights the imperative of addressing infrastructure gaps within public healthcare institutions and the dearth of skilled teleoncology professionals.

This study proposes a teleoncology model for the Indigenous community areas and other geographically isolated areas, especially the Lakshadweep and Andaman Nicobar Islands in India, based on an analysis of teleoncology benefits and challenges. The model incorporates elements from established telemedicine programs, including the Townville Cancer Center (TCC), Ontario Telehealth care Network (OTN) for Aboriginals, and the Cuban healthcare system. A review of the teleoncology networks, TCC and OTN, revealed the critical role of virtual consultation rooms nationwide, particularly in Lakshadweep, Andaman Nicobar Island and indigenous community areas in India. Findings from studies by Thaker et al. (2013)²⁰ underscore the importance of providing treatment at local health facilities, reducing long-distance travel for chemotherapy sessions or laboratory tests. This approach is economically beneficial and can reduce inter-hospital transfer²⁰.

Moreover, enabling synchronous (real-time) video conferencing sessions or asynchronous (recorded video consultations) with oncologists or health consultants at cancer centres reduces the need for in-person visits^{13,17}. This approach allows patients to stay in their villages during teleconsultations for pre and post-surgery, chemotherapy, and radiation therapy sessions, receiving treatment from the nearest telehealth centre. For example, through OTN, remote health care is provided electronically by one in four health professionals. Exploring the TCC model of health services emphasised the administration of telechemotherapy at the nearest health facility.

Sabesan and Kelly (2014)²² suggested that telehealth services can increase equity in healthcare delivery. Such services can be tailored to meet cultural needs and foster community engagement. Teleoncology applications have been extended to palliative care, radiology, pathology, and rehabilitation²². The accessibility of telehealth services and the ability to provide multidisciplinary care have made them particularly beneficial for underserved populations in remote areas, such as Lakshadweep, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, and tribal communities.

Recommendations

Leveraging existing infrastructure such as eSanjeevani and incorporating best practices from successful programs can establish a robust teleoncology model in India. This model should prioritise expanding internet connectivity, creating virtual consultation rooms, implementing telechemotherapy, integrating multidisciplinary care, developing a skilled workforce, and tailoring services to community needs. By utilizing the comprehensive network of eSanjeevani and the state-owned telehealth network, India can ensure equity in accessing oncology services regardless of geographic location and socioeconomic status. Moreover, teleoncology has the potential to reduce costs. From the researcher's perspective, this study provides data on cancer incidence, mortality, and treatment-associated information for evaluation and research. However, further research is necessary to evaluate cost-effectiveness and address digital literacy challenges to revolutionise medical care in India.

Limitations: Purposive selection of the articles in English may follow selection bias, excluding the relevant literature on teleoncology and its development in India after 2024. Moreover, more reviewers on the consensus may add diverse opinions on the introduction of teleoncology and the recent digital health development in the country.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained, No. IHEC/ CU/ 203/ 29; dated December 8, 2023.

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